

ASSESS THE EFFECT OF BUILDING MATERIAL PRICE FLUCTUATION ON PUBLIC BUILDING CONSTRUCTION PROJECT DELIVERY IN ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA FROM 2015- 2024

**Ezike Franklin Chukwuemeka, Ajaelu Henry C. and Okeke Francisca
Nkachukwu**

Department of Quantity Surveying, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu.

Corresponding Email: ezikefrankling@yahoo.com; ajaelu.henry@esut.edu.ng;
okekefrancisca90@yahoo.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17630131>

Keywords:

Building
Material Price
Fluctuation,
Public
Construction
Projects, Project
Delivery
Performance,
Construction
Industry
Challenges and
Enugu State,
Nigeria.

Abstract: Significant increase has brought about loss of client confidence in consultants, as well as added asset risks, inability of developers to deliver affordable housing. Therefore, the aim of this study is assess the effect of Building material price fluctuation on public building construction project delivery in Enugu State, Nigeria From 2015-2024 with following objectives: to ascertain the causes of building material price fluctuation on public building construction project in Enugu State and to evaluate its effect of building material price fluctuation on public building construction project in Enugu State. Descriptive survey research design was used for this study while primary data was collected through questionnaire, oral interviews and direct observation. The population of the study were Registered Builders, Registered Quantity Surveyors, Contractors, Estate Surveyors, Architects, and other professionals within the industry. Taro Yamane's was used to generate as a sample size which is 269.while a stratified random sampling was used in this study. Data collected for this research was analyzed with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 22 software. Findings shows that one of highest causes of building material price fluctuation on public building construction was exchange rate fluctuation which has the highest a mean index of 4.27 while the lowest is corruption and procurement issues has a mean index of 3.90. Hence, the study concludes that the identified items are the causes of Building material price fluctuation on public building construction project delivery in Enugu State which recommends that there is need to evaluate the cause which exist between the trend of building materials and building development so as to ensure an enhanced performance of the building industries in Enugu state is ensured at large and also there is need to monitor the hire in price by professionals in construction industries.

Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Building materials play a vital and crucial role in the construction industry as they are those materials put together in erecting buildings as

Ezike Franklin Chukwuemeka, Ajaelu Henry C. and Okeke Francisca Nkachukwu

cited by Onyejiaka, Nwoke, and Udobi, (2019). Construction project is not totally feasible without the inclusion of building materials. Previous studies in the building industry have indicated that building materials account for between 50 to 60% of the total construction input (Adedeji, 2022). Building materials constitute the largest single input in building construction, of which housing is one part. He further revealed that the cost of building materials has been one of the factors prohibiting successful public housing delivery. Housing is a key factor in the sustainable development of a nation and one of the three basic human needs (Ganiyu, 2016). This is true as the housing sector is the bedrock of the economy of most developed nations and an important tool for stimulating growth.

Moreover, most advanced countries like the United States of America, Britain and Canada, the sector contributes between 30 to 70% percent of their Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as asserted by Tropical Built Environment Journal. While decent housing is important to every individual and nation, housing crisis remains one of the global problems and a grave and rising challenge facing both urban and rural residents and public and private sectors, particularly in most developing countries. Developing nations are continuously challenged with issues of inadequate housing (Du Plessis, 2002). Housing demand continues to grow in recent periods worldwide and is projected to continue escalating the building materials (Morenkeji *et al* 2017).

In Malaysia, the price of building materials has rapidly increased from 0.1% in 2022 to 1.8% in

2023 with the increase in cost of construction materials such as cement, steel, sand and piling materials (Huan and Juaha 2013). This had made house prices especially in Bahru and Kuala Lumpur which is the capital city in Malaysia, very expensive and non-affordable to many citizens. This negative situation is not different in under developing countries where the price of building materials keeps increasing. Windapo and Cattell (2015) revealed that the price of building materials in South Africa among others have an effect on the cost of building a house. From the Construction Industry Development Bureau (CIDB) report of 2016 also, volatile building materials in the South

Africa construction industry are steel, cement, sand, copper, timber, PVC, bitumen and masonry block/bricks which according to the engineering new document cited within the CIDB report have increased up to 100% between October 2000 and October 2006. Statistics reveals that the average price increase of building materials in South Africa is 8.3% in 2022 whereas it increased to 12.9% in 2023 (National Association of Home Builders, 2024).

In Nigeria, the availability and adequacy of building materials partly determine the level of project development as well as the success of any housing policy and programme (Akanni *et al* 2014). In recognition of the indispensable nature of building materials in construction process in the country, it was specifically mentioned in section 6.1 of the 1991 National Housing Policy that building materials and its components constitute 50% to 60% of the total construction input.

Moreover, (Satprem 1990) observed that the exceptionally high cost in the price of building materials severely reduce the number of residential buildings built per year by both private individuals and government

In the Southeastern part of Nigeria especially in Enugu State, there has been a steady increase in the price of building materials which has affected the rate of construction projects by residents and investors. A study by Ofurum and Ihuah (2021) revealed that for ten (10) years (2011 to 2020), the cost of building materials was constantly, steadily and irreversibly increasing. From their study, a 50kg bag of cement increased from N1,600.00 in 2011 to N3,600.00 in 2020. Also hardcore trip of gravel increased from N14,500.00 in 2010 to N22,000 in 2019 and increased again to N35,000.00 in 2022. Also, a close observation from the figures of the report showed that all building materials products identified had all increased over the stipulated period of time.

More so, the consistent increase in the price of building materials have contributed to low housing development in the nation as only few people who can afford the materials erect structures (Oladipo *et al* 2012). Furthermore, this is believed to have led to building collapse witnessed in this recent period as majority of the building constructions going on are usually done with substandard materials (Oyedele *et al* 2006). It is on this gaps that the researcher tends to assess the effect of building material price fluctuation on public building construction project delivery in Enugu State within the time frame of 2015-2024, with following objectives: to ascertain the causes of building material price

fluctuation on public building construction projects in Enugu State and to evaluate its effect of building material price fluctuation on public building construction project in Enugu State.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Building Construction Industry

The building construction industry contributes significantly in terms of scale and share in the development process for both developed and developing countries. The construction products provide the necessary public infrastructure and private physical structures for many productive activities such as services, commerce, utilities and other industries. The industry is not only important for its finished product, but it also employs a large number of people (directly and indirectly) and therefore has an effect on the economy of a country/region during the actual construction process (AnOlatunji, 2010).

The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) put Nigeria's post-re-basing contributions of the construction sector to Gross Domestic Product at N5.7 billion in three years. NBS, in its summary report of 2010, 2011 and 2012 fiscal years on the Construction industry and disclosed that in 2010, the sector contributed N1.570 billion, a value which leaped by 21.30 per cent to reach N1.905 billion in 2011. The industry's contributions closed at N2.188 billion in 2012, bringing the total contribution of the sector to GDP to N5.7 billion and 2017 report shows that the sector recorded a 13 percent growth. Construction activities captured in the report include construction of buildings, roads, railways as well as civil engineering projects. Others are construction of utility projects,

demolitions as well as site preparations, among others (shittu et al 2021).

The building construction industry in Enugu State is experiencing significant growth, driven by government initiatives, private sector participation, and a focus on sustainable development. Under the leadership of Governor Peter Mbah, Enugu State has embarked on an ambitious infrastructure agenda. As of December 2024, there are approximately 1,000 active construction sites across the state, encompassing projects such as smart green schools, Type 2 health centers, and the completion of landmarks like the International Conference Centre and Hotel Presidential. In March 2025, the government initiated the second phase of urban road construction in Enugu metropolis, aiming to enhance the state's infrastructure and improve the quality of life for residents. Additionally, the Enugu Megacity Project, launched in October 2023, aims to develop a new city with modern amenities and infrastructure, covering over 300,000 hectares across multiple local government areas (Ngwu, 2025).

2.1.1 Building Materials in Nigeria

Building materials play a vital role in the construction industry as they are those materials put together in erecting buildings; construction project is not feasible without the inclusion of building materials (Akanniet, 2014). That is, building materials play an undeniable significant role in the housing industry as it is the most substantial input in project development. As discussed by Adedeji (2012), about 60% of total housing expenditure is spent on building materials.

Notably, Mekson (2011) indicated that appropriate use of the building materials, in respect of the expertise involved in the building construction process, determines the strength, functionality and quality of the building. Building materials play a crucial role in enhancing sustainability of buildings and contributing to economic wealth of the nation. However, Mohammed (2008) observed that in order to reduce construction costs, and to improve productivity, quality and timely project delivery, material management effectiveness must be a main concern. The prices of building materials increase on a daily basis, due to instability of the Naira to the Dollar and general inflationary trends.

2.1.2 Price Fluctuation of Building Materials in Nigeria

The beginning of inflation in Nigeria can be said to be in 1951 when ministerial government was introduced. (Solanke 2015) mentioned that the Nigerian economy registered low rates of inflation in the years immediately after independence; this was mainly as a result of the civil war. Mojekwu 2013 established that since the end of the Nigeria civil war in 1970 and especially following the introduction of the structural adjustment programme SAP, in 1986, urban housing construction costs and house rents have been rising at uncomfortable rates. Mekson (2008) defined inflation as a general rise in the price level in an area over a certain period of time. Therefore, the goal of most countries is the desire to maintain a stable price level (CBN, 2016). Memom (2011) supports this assertion by further surmising that price stability is one of the principal economic goals in any

economy. Memom (2011)) however argues that this appears to be a tall order given the incidence of inflation presently ravaging economies of the world especially developing ones.

Shittu et al (2015) explained inflation to be a condition of general and persistent rise in prices. An economy is thus regarded as suffering from inflation if it is undergoing a period of continuously rising prices (Olatunji, 2010). Inflation is measured in periods sufficiently long enough to eliminate bias arising from short-term. The chief measure of inflation is the inflation rate, which is the percentage rate of change of price index over time (CBN, 2021).

Inflation is one of the intractable problems facing Nigerian economy. Inflation has been considered to be a direct result of the policies of the country's governments.

The beginning of inflation in Nigeria can be said to be in 1951 when ministerial government was introduced. Memom (2011) mentioned that the Nigerian economy registered low rates of inflation in the years immediately after independence; this was mainly as a result of the civil war. Nwuba and Rumane (2007) established that since the end of the Nigeria civil war in 1970 and especially following the introduction of the structural adjustment programme SAP, in 1986, urban housing construction costs and house rents have been rising at uncomfortable rates. This situation has resulted in serious urban housing problems resulting in multiplicity of slum settlements and shanty towns

Sanvido *et al* (1992) the oil boom of the 1970s brought with it fundamental changes in the Nigerian economy, the structure of policy

incentives and controls encouraged import oriented production and consumption pattern with little incentives for non-oil exports. Again, the competitiveness of the agricultural sector in the world market was eroded by overvalued naira exchange rate, inadequate pricing policies, rural-urban migration and neglect arising from 'too much oil syndrome'. Akanni et al (2014) recorded that these inflationary trends had rippling effect on the Nigerian construction industry.

There is no gainsaying the fact that the importance of construction to the Nigerian economy cannot be overemphasized. Unfortunately, this sub sector has been one of the worst hit by the debilitating effects of inflation. Jagboro and Oweye (2014) emphasized that successive governments in Nigeria have used the construction industry as a regulator of the economy as it constitutes a large proportion of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Solanke (2015); Mekson (2008) affirmed the construction industry to be the prime motivator of the Nigerian economy; it represents 60% of the capital investment and 30 percent of GDP. Similarly, Oladipo (2012) describes the construction industry as a barometer for measuring the economic growth of Nigeria.

2.2 Causes of Building Material Price Fluctuation on Public Building Construction Project

The factors responsible for increases in the cost of building materials have been categorized as, Human related Factors, Stakeholders related factors, Economic related factors and External factors as partly recorded by Mekson (2008).

2.2 .1 Human factors

There are three typical resources associated with construction: material, machinery and manpower (3Ms). Manpower is the source of more threats than construction materials and machinery (Hanna et al., 2015). In the study of Windapo and Cattell (2022), as they sought to benchmark respondents' perceptions against actual factors that may affect future building material prices in South Africa, it was revealed that labour cost had the highest correlation with building material prices, followed by transport cost. Notably, poor communication between management and labour can reduce morale of the labourers further decreasing production while increasing project cost. Nwachukwu (2016) pointed out effective communication management as a key factor for improving the management of human resources in construction. This exposes the need of an efficient and effective project manager whose role involves liaising between labour and management.

2.2.2 Stakeholder Related Factors

Supplier default: Nega (2008) found the factors responsible for supplier default come from the fact that some suppliers control a monopoly of the market by keeping the price high and restricting the output, showing little or no awareness of the needs of the customers. The researchers stressed that because of the high demand of some building materials, some suppliers wait for a high accumulation of orders, thereby generating problems associated with importing raw materials as well as increased exchange rates. The results of the study of also revealed that fraudulent practices and kickbacks was the second significant factor responsible for

an increase in construction cost as perceived by construction professionals interviewed.

Improper planning: *Improper planning* is one of the most important factors affecting the cost of building materials. Contractors should utilize all resources in effective ways. Proper scheduling is essential in project resource utilization, as the reverse, inadequate planning, will increase the project cost (Eshofonie, 2018), suggesting that where there is no effective contractor scheduling and planning on site, these factors will be responsible for construction project delays.

Delay in the supply of building materials: Timely delivery of building materials is essential. To this end, Windapo (2012) revealed that quite a number of projects during building production processes experienced extensive delays in the supply of building materials, thereby exceeding the initial budgeted cost. Unavailability of building materials at the required time on site during construction frequently results in production materials deterioration and wastages, time wastage, low labour productivity and production cost overruns (Solanke, 2015). However, an effective material management system is significant during construction and for this, identification of materials should be made prior to the time of using the materials. This is an important step in avoiding late delivery of materials (Rahas stated by the scholar,

Client contribution to design change: While a change in a project's design can arise for any number of reasons, Eshofonie, (2018) acknowledged that clients are actually the major cause of change for many reasons: it could be for marketing purposes or due to an economic

situation to meet customer demands. Also, adjustment or change might occur as a result of newly-emerging concepts perceived by the client for the project to achieve anticipated functional requirements. Olatunije (2010) further confirmed that clients initiate most of changes in building design which are likely to extend the delivery of projects at construction costs higher than budgeted cost. Arguably, changes ordered by clients will bear a consequence on the period of construction activities and increase the construction materials cost. A number of other studies have also shown that design changes are primarily caused by clients (Love, Frani, & Edwards, 2002; Memon *et al.*, 2014; Olatunije (2010)).

2.2 .3 Economic related factors

Exchange rates: The exchange rate is the price of a nation's currency in terms of another currency used in determining the strength of one currency against another. Thus, an exchange rate has two components, the domestic currency and a foreign currency. Nigeria produces its own strategic materials and has the ability to survive without importation but yet relies on imported equipment. Therefore, increases in materials cost within the industry are a cause for concern. The skyrocketing exchange rate of the dollar to the naira (1 dollar=362 naira as at 1st August 2018) is killing the building materials sector in Nigeria and depreciation in naira value is working against the building materials importers.

Inflation: Inflation is a sustained increase in the price level of goods and services in an economy over a period of time. Consequently, inflation reflects a reduction in the purchasing

power per unit of money, a loss of real value in the medium of exchange and unit of account within the economy. Clearly, any other factor that delays a project will further expose the project to the risk of inflationary cost increases. iii. Interest rate the high interest rate of banks and the unpredictability in the foreign exchange market result in serious depletion of a nation's foreign exchange resources, harshly affecting the industry with import dependence of about 60% of its raw materials (Jagboro & Owoye, 2004). However, Oladapo (2022) opined that across the nation, many construction and profitable real estate projects and housing have either been put on hold or abandoned half way because of the scarcity of capital or because of the sky rocketing cost of borrowing. Aside from the increase in the cost of borrowing, high interest rate also causes reduction in spending as people are more inclined to save. Central Bank of Nigeria interest rate as at April, 2018 was 14%.

Fluctuation in the cost of building materials: The studies of Rahman *et al.* (2023) revealed that fluctuation in cost of building materials was ranked as a significant factor of cost overrun. Incessant fluctuation of building materials is the most severe cause of project cost escalation. Akanni *et al.* (2014) conducted a study to identify the factors causing cost overrun in Ethiopia. Findings revealed that the main cause of cost overrun was fluctuations in cost of building materials, a fluctuation attributable to the limitation in exchange rate which in turn affects building material cost and the general cost level. In addition to exchange rate, others such as inflation, hoarding by suppliers and

government policies also cause fluctuation in the cost of building materials.

Inadequate production of raw materials:

Oyedele et al (2006) argue that the reason for shortage of materials could be the ineffective supply of materials occasioned by general shortages in the industry, poor communication amidst sites and head office, poor purchasing planning and poor material coordination. Shortages of some construction materials may arise where the level of development activity is unusually high. If this had not been anticipated and integrated into the original cost estimate, the prices of these materials will increase as asserted by (Ihuah and Benebo 2014). This can also occur where the sector relies heavily on importation than exploiting locally sourced ones.

Supply and demand of building materials:

Supply and demand of materials will determine the price of building materials. Windapo, (2022) stated that the demand for more housing and delay in supplying the building materials (or lack of materials) will add to the trends in the price of building materials where the law of supply and demand can be related. They further admitted that building materials cost increases are dependent on the market conditions under which they are manufactured. For example, the researchers noted that material cost will increase if only one or two companies are manufacturing building materials as compared to those for which many manufacturers compete for the same market. This is true as certain brands enjoy monopoly in the building materials sector and their demands are usually higher than others. A precondition for cost-effective construction is the availability of construction materials at the

required time and location on site. Delay in the supply of materials on site is one causative factor of cost overruns in construction projects, particularly in developing countries.

2.2.4 External Factors

Force majeure: Force majeure otherwise known as 'Acts of God' is a term that covers a range of events, including revolution, war, riot, earthquake, landslide, fire, political and economic instability and other such risks (Ihuah 2015). Where it occurs, it will result in significant increase in the cost of building materials especially when reconstruction comes to mind.

Weather conditions: While building materials are a significant component of any building project, climate change directly or indirectly will also have an effect on the use of building materials before or during building construction. Climate changes contribute a vast challenge to global warming emission of CO₂ by buildings under construction and in use (Windapo, 2023). As actual site conditions for a construction project are not usually determined until construction begins, some changes may occur due to hostile weather conditions or changes in sub-soil conditions (EU Framework, 2018).

Government policies: According to Mansfield, Ugwu, and Obadan (2021), the building materials sector is one the government policies established. Government policies on importation, taxation, interest rate, relief to local producers, budget etc. impact on how building materials affect housing delivery. Harris (2012), incited governments may also invoke their powers to initiate or halt projects on political, social and environmental grounds. It is

important to note that no construction work happens in a single space; rather it is subject to a group of powers from regulatory control to political intervention. Among other external factors responsible for increase in cost of building materials is the lack of proxy substitutes for some building materials. Construction project consideration Cost, quality and time are the three major factors significantly essential in any construction project. Nonetheless, the primary goal of the construction project manager is accomplishing successful completion of the construction project within the predefined time, budgeted cost and expected quality checks (Nwachukwu 2016). Kerzner (2023) emphasized that the process of project management is labelled successful when the project objectives are achieved within time, cost and desired technological level.

2.2.5 Building Production Related Factors

Site related factors: Construction waste becomes a universal concern faced by construction stakeholders. Waste generated during construction activities on site can affect delivery of a construction project significantly, specifically on construction cost, construction time, productivity and sustainability aspects (Nagapan, 2012). He also recorded that the majority of waste generated during construction is materials waste, primarily as a result of the use of un-reusable materials, leftovers and debris. Unfortunately, this material waste amounts about 9% of the weight of materials purchased (Azis, 2013). Material mismanagement during construction can lead to an increase in costs of construction, whereas effective management of materials can bring extensive savings to project

costs. Increase in material cost is primarily due to increase in transport charges (Windapo & Cattell, 2012). For example, Eshofonie (2008) noted that an increase in the cost of fuel will result in drastic increases in transportation costs. Hence, manufacturers raise the cost of building materials to cover the fuel increase when distributing the finished products from factory to suppliers and end-users.

Design related factors: A construction project performance is inevitably impacted by design changes (Nwuba (2004). Design change is a kind of change that impacts the method of work as was originally planned budgeted or scheduled (Abdul-Rahman, 2015). However, it was further revealed by researchers that changes do frequently arise at any stage of a project due to a variety of reasons stemming from diverse sources – with significant impact. Osegbo (2021) and Soham and Rajiv (2023) stated that the non-challenge attitude of design professionals to drawing queries (clarity, complexity and drawing errors) and inadequacies of information for production mean design challenges on construction projects. Oyedele and Tham (2016) affirmed that there must be excellent communication between design team members, including simplicity, certainty, briefness and completeness of the design. Similarly, team-related matters such as team building, teamwork, team organization and team experience are frequently acknowledged as essential factors for project performance (Sanvido, 2021). Hence, lack of significant consideration for these matters in the design phase may extend the project duration leading to cost overruns (Idoro and Jalaiyo 2020). Design

change is connected to additional work, due to the absence of comprehensive briefing on the economic, functional and technical requirements of the project by the clients (Nwachukwu 2016). Abdul-Rahman, (2015) emphasized that design change orders resulting in additional work can account for as much as 50% of project cost overrun – quite substantial! Furthermore, additional work is a significant factor contributing to cost increases and schedule delays in construction projects. Wrong methods of estimation can be ascribed to lack of satisfactory experience of quantity surveyors (Nwuba, 2004). Arguably, all these factors impinge significantly on the cost of materials.

2.3 Effects of Building Materials Cost on Public Building Delivery in Enugu

Fluctuation in cost of construction:

Windapo and Cattell (2023) stated that substantial growth in the construction industry is subject to price stability in materials costs as these have increased at faster rates than the expected. Client and project contractors have been facing serious issues to maintain steady cost projection on construction projects (Zhou. and Zhao (2013). Also, poor estimation of original project cost and underestimating the construction cost by quantity surveyors are the basic reasons of cost escalation in construction industry. The researcher further stated that the prices change so quickly that the initial budget figures become completely unrealistic. Akanni et al. (2024), in their study of the implications of the rising cost of building materials in Nigeria, determined fluctuation in construction costs as the most significant effect of increase in the cost building materials. This is in agreement with

Ofurum and Ihuah, (2021). Who found out that on the key issue affecting the development of the construction industry in Nigeria that increase in costs of building materials was a significant factor affecting development of the construction industry.

Increase in project abandonment: Project abandonment is the unplanned suspension of the work progress especially at the execution stage such as the refusal or failure to complete a contract after practical completion time (Nwachukwu, 2016). Numerous construction projects are temporarily or even permanently abandoned, and he also observed the predominance of many uncompleted and abandoned projects resulted from finance related crises and material related factors. Inflation and high cost of building materials are major factors that lead to uncompleted and sub-standard buildings and this has a significant effect on the industry for delivery of housing. Whereas Aluko (2018) stated the effects of abandoned project on environment and identified such effects as the problems of flooding, traffic congestion, air and water pollution, drug addiction and health hazards in the neighbourhood. Also an upward review of contract sum leads to conflicts between contractors and clients, likely leading to cases of abandonment where investments are tied down, since such project will not be put to use at the expected time.

Low volume of construction product: Output of the construction industry in South Africa is quite low when compared with the construction industry in many developed countries. Ganiyu (2016) stated that the South

African construction industry is faced with a number of threats, primarily affecting its performance in sustainable housing delivery. Similarly, according to a study by Windapo (2024), in Nigeria millions of middle and low income families are being priced out of the market for home ownership due to the excessive increase in the cost of building materials and the consequential acute shortages of housing. The observations from these studies were due to the increase in the cost of building materials. It has been confirmed that Nigeria has more than 17 million housing deficit as at 2004 (Uwani, 2017).

Poor quality of workmanship: Lam, Chan, Wong and Wong (2017) assigned that output of quality buildings and structures is one of the attributes of a developed construction industry. The quality of workmanship in construction work is assessed according to the requirement of the relevant standard, and marks are awarded if the workmanship complies with this standard (CIDB, 2021). The study of Oladipo and Oni (2022) reporting the trend in the cost of building materials has envisaged great danger for the construction industry and the nation's economy. The researchers further claimed that there were records of conflicts between clients and building contractors over review in contract sums, so to avoid conflicts and still be in the business, some

contractors fell back upon substandard or insufficient materials for construction projects, an action which contributed to cases of building collapse. Undeniably, workmanship plays an important role in project quality. Akanni, (2014) further revealed low quality workmanship and inhibited innovations in construction methods as further repercussions of building materials cost increases. Hence, the studies revealed that increases in the cost of building materials contribute to low and unreliable rates of profitability of contractors as attempts to balance up by enticing contractors to employ low quality workmanship, prohibiting new innovations in the construction methods.

3.0 Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was used for this study while primary data was collected through questionnaire, oral interviews and direct observation. The population of the study were Registered Builders, Registered Quantity Surveyors, Contractors, Estate Surveyors, Architects, and other professionals within the industry. Taro Yamane's was used to generate as a sample size which is 269.while a stratified random sampling was used in this study. Data collected for this research was analyzed with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 22 software.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Ascertain the causes of building material price fluctuation on public building construction project.

Table 4.1: The causes of building material price fluctuation on public building construction

S/ No	The causes of building material price fluctuation on public building construction	SA 5	A 4	UD 3	D 2	SD 1	ΣFX	INDEX	RAN K
1	Exchange rate volatility	130 650	111 444	6 18	15 30	7 7	269 1149	4.27	1st
2	Inflation	128 640	108 432	8 24	18 36	7 7	269 1139	4.23	2nd
3	Insecurity and Instability	125 625	101 404	10 30	22 44	11 11	269 1114	4.14	3rd
4	Transportation cost	122 610	98 392	8 24	20 40	21 21	269 1087	4.04	5th
5	Government policies	120 600	96 384	10 30	23 46	20 20	269 1080	4.01	7th
6	Demand and supply imbalance	118 590	100 400	12 36	25 50	14 14	269 1090	4.05	4 th
7	Global market influence	112 560	112 448	5 15	20 40	20 20	269 1083	4.03	6th
8	Speculation and hoarding	110 550	100 400	11 33	26 52	22 22	269 1057	3.93	8th
9	Corruption and procurement issues	102 510	112 448	8 24	22 44	25 25	269 1051	3.90	9th
10	Population size	99 495	99 396	15 45	25 50	31 31	269 1017	3.7	10 th
	Grand Mean							4.03	

Source: Researcher's field survey 2025

Table 4.1 above shows that the causes of building material price fluctuation on public building construction are, exchange rate fluctuation has a mean index of 4.27, high rate of inflation has a mean index of 4.23, insecurity and instability has a mean index of 4.14, transportation cost has a mean index of 4.04, government policies has a mean index of 4.01, demand and supply of building material has a mean index of 4.05, global market influence has a mean index of 4.03, speculation and hoarding has a mean index of 3.93, corruption and procurement issues has a mean index of 3.90 while population size has a mean index of 3.7. Hence, the study concludes that the identified items are the causes of building material price fluctuation on public building construction

Examine the effect of building material price fluctuation on public building construction project in Enugu State.

Table 4.2

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.000000	1.10E-10	0.000000	0.0000
CMT	-3.260814	3.12E-14	-1.045172	0.3205
SB	-0.463526	2.652535	-1.836266	0.5367
RF	-6.037715	3.10E-14	-0.194707	0.8495
SND	-1.081114	8.39E-15	-3.288203	0.0267
GRNT	-1.063550	1.11E-15	-9.039814	0.4556
TMB	-0.023811	2.93E-13	-5.483733	0.0450

The regression results A priori test are presented as follows

In the regression result, the variables under consideration are public building construction project (dependent variable), people course of rework, process course of rework and environment course of rework (independent variables). From the result, the estimated coefficient values of $b_0, b_1, - b_{12}$, are 3.260814, 0.463526, 6.037715, 1.081114, 1.063550, 0.023811, 0.044554, 0.098483, 1.288377, 4.733662, 0.488399 and 0.778229 respectively (see appendix iv, for the confirmation of the data for the analyses of the result).

Dependent Variable: BPD

Method: Least Squares

Date: 10/23/24 Time: 04:44

Sample (adjusted): 2013 2022

Included observations: 9 after adjustments

R-squared	0.662500	Mean dependent var	40454.55
Adjusted squared	R-0.592760	S.D. dependent var	20439.75
S.E. of regression	1.52E-11	Akaike info criterion	- 46.67952
Sum squared resid	2.31E-21	Schwarz criterion	- 46.08440
Log likelihood	525.4747	Hannan-Quinn-criter.	- 46.53933
F-statistic	3.45E+30	Durbin-Watson stat	1.766476
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Source: E Views 12 Computation 2024

Where,

CMT = Cement

SB = Sancrete Block

RF = Reinforcement

SND = Sand

GRNT = Granite

TMB = Timber

Evaluation of Regression Results

Evaluation Based on Economic Criterion

This subsection is concerned with evaluating the error correction mechanism result based on a priori expectations. The signs and magnitude of each variable coefficient is evaluated against theoretical expectations.

The signs of some of the variable's coefficient from the estimated model are in line with a priori expectations. The coefficient value of cement, sandcrete block, reinforcement, sand, granite, timber on the building project development is negative such that an increase in the price of cement, sandcrete, reinforcement, sand, granite,

timber will lead to decrease in the building project development overtime.

Evaluation Based on Statistical Criterion

This subsection applies the R^2 , the t-test and the f-test to determine the statistical reliability of the estimated parameters. These tests are performed as follows;

R^2 –Result and Interpretation

The coefficient of determination, R^2 , is given as 0.662500; this implies that 0.662500 percent of the variation in building project development is being explained by the variations in cement, sand, reinforcement, sand, granite and timber. Thus, the R^2 which yielded 66.2500 percent means that the explanatory powers of the independent variables: cement, sand, reinforcement, sand, granite and timber, over the dependent variable (building project development), are averagely high. Hence, the variables have good better or even better goodness of fit.

t–Test Result and Interpretation

We also employ the 95% confidence interval or 5% level of significance (that is, $5/100=0.05$, $0.05/2=0.025$) and 39 as our degree of freedom. From the distribution table, $t_{0.025,39} = 2.042$. The result of the t-test of significance is shown in table 5.5 below:

Table 4.3: Result of t-Test of Significance on of the effect of building material price fluctuation on public building construction project in Enugu State.

Variables	t-computed (t*)	t-tabulated ($t_{\alpha/2}$)	Conclusion
CMT	-1.045172	2.042	Insignificant
SB	-1.836266	2.042	Insignificant
RF	-0.194707	2.042	Insignificant
SND	-3.288203	2.042	Significant
GRNT	-9.039814	2.042	Significant
TMB	-5.483733	2.042	Significant

Significant (Reject H_0 ; accept H_1),
Insignificant (Accept H_0).

From the t- test result above, for CMT, $t^* < t_{\alpha/2}$, that is, $-1.045172 > 2.042$, therefore the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence cement is statistically insignificant, thus cement has insignificant impact on building project development in Enugu State.

For SB, $t^* < t_{\alpha/2}$, that is, $-1.836266 > 2.042$, therefore the null hypothesis accepted. Hence sancrete block is statistically insignificant, thus sancrete block has insignificant impact on building project development in Enugu state.

For RF, $t^* < t_{\alpha/2}$, that is, $-0.194707 > 2.042$, therefore the null hypothesis accepted. Hence reinforcement is statistically insignificant, thus

The result of the t-test is presented below and evaluated based on the critical value (2.042) and the value of calculated t-statistics for each variable.

reinforcement has insignificant impact on building project development in Enugu state.

For SND, $t^* > t_{\alpha/2}$, that is, $-3.288203 > 2.042$, therefore the null hypothesis rejected. Hence sand is statistically significant, thus sand has insignificant impact on building project development in Enugu state.

For GRNT, $t^* > t_{\alpha/2}$, that is, $-9.039814 > 2.042$, therefore the null hypothesis rejected. Hence granite is statistically significant, thus granite has significant impact on building project development in Enugu state.

For TMB, $t^* > t_{\alpha/2}$, that is, $-5.483733 > 2.042$, therefore the null hypothesis rejected. Hence

timber is statistically significant, thus timber has significant impact on building project development in Enugu state.

Result and Interpretation of f-Test of Significance on the effect of building material price fluctuation on public building construction project in Enugu State.

The degree of freedom for the numerator (V_1) and for the denominator (V_2) are given as $K-1$ and $n-K$

Where

$N =$ sample size = 11

$K =$ number of parameters including the constant term = 4

$V_1 = 3 - 1 = 2$, $V_2 = 11 - 3 = 8$, $df = (2, 8)$ at 5% level of significance and $df = (2, 8)$, $f_{0.05} = 2.92$ and $F^* = 3.637090$. Since $f^* > f_{0.05}$, therefore, the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This implies that the independent variables (cement, sandcrete block, reinforcement, sand, granite, timber, casement window, aluminum, ceramic tiles, wooden doors, emulsion paint and PVC ceiling), have joint influence on building project development in Enugu state Nigeria. Thus, the entire regression plane is significant.

Evaluation Based on Econometric Criterion

Normality Test Result and Interpretation on of the effect of building material price fluctuation on public building construction project in Enugu State.

The Normality test were done using the Jarque-Bera test of normality. Jarque-Bera test of normality is hinged on the hypothesis that K is close to or exactly 3 and S is close to or exactly 0, thus making the JB value close to or equal to 0, which is the condition for normal distribution.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of the research were used to assess the effect of building material price fluctuation on public building construction project delivery in Enugu State, Nigeria from 2015-2024

In Conclusion, It has been discovered in this research that there is a consistent increase in the trends of price building materials which have triggered a lot of challenges in the building development in Nigeria within the time frame captured in the study.

The study also comes to conclusion that the identified items such as exchange rate fluctuation with a mean index of 4.01, high rate of inflation with a mean index of 3.87, high rate of interest rate with a mean index of 3.84, fluctuation in the cost of building materials with a mean index of 3.75, inadequate production of raw materials with a mean index of 3.68, supply and demand of building materials has a mean index of 3.60, supply default with a mean index of 3.54, improper planning has a mean index of 3.49, force majeure has a mean index of 3.42 while weather conditions with a mean index of 3.34 are the factors affecting the building materials price trends on building development in Nigeria within the time frame of 2015-2024. Finally, the study also concluded that the building material price fluctuation has affected the building development in the selected states in the Enugu, Nigeria.

5.2 Recommendations for Performance Improvement

Based on the findings of the study, the study recommends the followings:

There is need to examine the direction of the relationship which exist between the building material price fluctuation and building development so as to ensure an enhanced performance of the building industries in the selected states in the Enugu and Nigeria at large. The identified factors which are responsible for building material price fluctuation such as high rate of fluctuation, interest rate gap, and inflation should be properly handled by governments, non-governmental organizations and stakeholders in the building industries so as

References

Abdul-Rahman, H., Wang, C. & Yap, J.B.H. (2015). Impacts of design changes on construction project performance. 14th Management in Construction Research Association (MiCRA 2015) Annual Conference and General Meeting.

Akanni, P.O., Oke, A.E. & Omotilewa, O.J., (2014). Implications of Rising Cost of Building Materials in Lagos State Nigeria. SAGE Open, 4(4), p.2158244014561213

Du Plessis, C. (2002). Agenda 21 for sustainable construction in developing countries. CSIR Report BOU E, 204.

Esohofonie, F. P. (2008). Factors Affecting Cost of Construction in Nigeria. Unpublished Master's Dissertation, University of Lagos, Nigeria

Ganiyu, B.O. (2016). Strategy to enhance sustainability in affordable housing

to enhance building operations in the selected areas.

More so, there is need to beef up the local content of our domestic building materials as it was witnessed from the study that one of the factors that causes the consistent increase in the price of building materials is imported inflation. Hence, government and relevant authorities in the building industries should strive to enhance the local content of our domestic building materials. There is need for thorough check by building professionals in order to monitor and control hike of building materials in project delivery

construction in South Africa (Doctoral dissertation, Cape Peninsula University of Technology).

Harris, O.J., (2012). Implications of Rising Cost of Building Materials in Lagos State Nigeria. SAGE Open, 4(4), p.2158244014561213.

Huan, Z. & Jianhua, Z. (2013) Analysis of Factors Causing Price Change of Building Materials. Advanced Materials Research, 683, 668-671. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.683.668>

Idoro, G. I., & Jolaiya, O. (2020). Evaluating material storage strategies and their relationship with construction project performance. Proceedings of CIB International Conference on Building Education and Research, University of Cape Town.

- Idoro, P. & Jollaiye (2020). Nigerian groans under high cost of building material. The Daily Sun.
- Ihuah, P.W. (2015,) Building materials costs increases and sustainability in real estate development in Nigeria. *Afr. I. Econ. Sustain. Sustain. Dev.* 4, 218-233[CrossRef]
- Ihuah, P.W. & Benebo, A.M. (2014) 'An assessment of the causes and effects of abandonment of development projects on real property values in Nigeria', *International Journal of Research in Applied, Natural and Social Sciences*, Vol. 2, No. 5, pp. 25036.
- Ihuah, P.W., Kakulu, I.I & Eaton, D. (2014) 'A review of critical project management success factors (CPMSF) for sustainable social housing in Nigeria', *International Journal of Sustainable Built Environment*, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp.62-71.
- Jagboro, G.O. & Owoeye, C.O. (2014). A model for predicting the prices of building materials using the exchange rate in Nigeria. *The Malaysian Surveyor*, 5(6):9-14.
- Mekson, J. (2008, August). Prices change of building materials in developing communities in Nigeria. The Professional Builders, pp. 21-27.
- Memon, A.H., Rahman, I.A., Abdullah, M.R. & Azis, A.A.A. (2011). Factors affecting construction cost in Mara large construction project: perspective of project management consultant. *International Journal of Sustainable Construction Engineering and Technology*, 1(2):41-54.
- Mohammed, H. Y. (2008). Nigeria: Builders groan on rising cost of building materials. Daily Trust, p. 29.
- Morenikeji, W., Umaru, E., Pai, H., Jiya, S. & Idowu, O. (2017). Spatial analysis of housing quality in Nigeria. *International Journal of Sustainable Built Environment*, 6, 309316, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijse.2017.03.008>
- Mojekwu, J.N., Idowu, A. & Sode, O., (2013). Analysis of the contribution of imported and locally manufactured cement to the growth of gross domestic product (GDP) of Nigeria (1986-2011). *African Journal of Business Management*, 7(5), p.360
- Nagapan, S., Rahman, I.A., Asmi, A., Memon, A.H. & Latif, I. (2012). December. Issues on construction waste: the need for sustainable waste management. In *Humanities, Science and Engineering (CHUSER), Colloquium on (325-330)*. IEEE.
- Nega, F. (2008). Causes and effects of cost overrun on public building construction projects in Ethiopia. Unpublished

doctoral dissertation, Addis Ababa University, Ethiopia.

- Nwachukwu, N.M (2016). A procedure for Multi-criteria Selection of Building Assemblies Automation in Construction, 12(5).
- Nwuba, B. (2004). Valuation of Price Fluctuation on Bldg Contracts. Journal of Institute of quality Surveyour 8:23-24
- Ofurum, C.G.; & Ihuah, P.W. (2021). An Analysis of the Trend in Cost of Building Materials on Property development in Owerri urban, Imo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Circuit, computer and Network*, 2(2), 30-35.
- Onyejiaka, Joseph Chukwudi, Nwoke, Victoria Obianuju & Udobi, Alexander Nnamdi (2019) Analysis of The Effects of High Cost of Building Materials on Public Housing Delivery in Awka, Anambra State. *Tropical Built Environment Journal*.
- Oladipo, F. O., & Oni, O. J. (2012). Review of selected macroeconomic factors impacting Building material prices in developing countries—A case of Nigeria. *Ethiopian Journal of Environmental Studies and Management*, 5, 131-137.
- Olatunji, O.A. (2010). The impact of oil price regimes on construction cost in Nigeria. *Journal of Construction Management and Economics*, 28(7), 747 – 759.
- Oyedele, O. & Tham, W. (2006). Client ‘assessment of architects’ performance in building delivery process: evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of building and environment*, 2090-2099.
- Rumana, R. (2007). Traditional House of Bangladesh: Typology of House According to Materials and Location. Virtual Conference on Sustainable Architectural Design and Urban Planning Asia SustainabilityNet.upc.edu, September, 2007
- Sanvido V, Grobler F, Parfitt K, & Guvenis M. (1992). Critical success factors for construction projects. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, ASCE; 118(1):94-111.
- Satprem, M. (1999) Seminar on earth architecture at Alliance Française DeColombo, conducted by Auroville Building Center, India.
- Shittu, A. A. Idiako, J. E. & Akanmu, W. P. (2015). Effect of Petroleum Price Increase on Cost of Selected Building Finishing Materials in the Nigerian Construction Industry (2006-2012). *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 6(8).
- Shittu, A. A., Adamu, A. D., Oyeniyi, A.K. & Shehu, M. A. (2013). Influence of Prices of Selected Building Materials on the

Rate of Housing Development in Minna (2003 – 2012).

Soham, M. & Rajiv, B. (2013). Critical factors affecting labour productivity in construction projects: case study of South Gujarat region of India. *International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology*, 2(4):583-591.

Solanke, B.H. (2015). Effective strategy for construction materials procurement during Construction towards the enhancement of sustainable building production in Western Cape, South Africa (Doctoral dissertation, Cape Peninsula University of Technology)

Windapo, A, Olugboyega O, Pomponi F., Moghayedi A. & Emuze, Fidelis (2012). Causality between challenges, availability, and extent of use of local building materials. *S. Afr. j. sci.* vol.118 n.7-8 Pretoria Jun./Aug. 2022 [http s://doi .org/10.1 7159/sajs .2022/9534](http://doi.org/10.17159/sajs.2022/9534)

Windapo, A. & Cattell, K. (2012) “Examine the Trends in Building Material Prices”: Build Environment Stakeholders’ Perspectives. In Proceedings of the Joint CIB International Symposium of W055, W065 and W118, TG46, TG81 and TG84. *International Conference on Construction Management Research: Management of Construction-Research to Practice*, Montreal, QC, Canada.

Zhou H. and Zhao J. H. (2013). Analysis of Factors to Cause the Price Change of Building Materials *Advanced Materials Research* Vol. 683. 668-671.

Emmitt, S. (2014) “Selection and specification of building products: Implications for design managers. *Architectural Engineering and Design Management*”. 2:176-186.

Egwaikhide, S. O. (2019). *Housing development in Nigeria, which way forward*. The Professional Builders.

Evcı, M.M. & Ciravoglu, A. (2015). An evaluation of the role of environmental, social and economic factors in architects’ choice of building materials. *Megaron* 10(2), 139-148.

Faremi, O.J, Ajayi, O.O, & Faremi, O.E, (2020) Factors Influencing the Use of Substandard Materials in the Construction of Residential Buildings, *CSID Journal of Infrastructure Development*:3(1):40-50.

Flanaga, D. (2021). The role of logistics in the materials flow control process. *Construction Management & Economics*, 16(2):131-137.

Froeschle, L.M. (1999). Environmental assessment and specification of green building materials. *Construction Specifier*, 52:53-57.

Gbadebo, M.A (2014) “Promoting the use of alternative building technologies in Nigerian Construction Industry. The Problems and recommendations”, *International Journal of Advancements in Research and Technology*, vol. 3, no. 11, pp. 69-73.

Ganiyu, B.O. (2016). Strategy to enhance sustainability in affordable housing construction in South Africa (Doctoral dissertation, Cape Peninsula University of Technology).

Harris, O.J., (2012). Implications of Rising Cost of Building Materials in Lagos State Nigeria. *SAGE Open*, 4(4), p.2158244014561213.

Herda, G., Sangori, R, & Bock, M. (2017). “Low cost low carbon, no Data: Kenya’s struggle to Develop the Availability of Performance Data for Building Products”, *Procedia Environmental Sciences*, 38: 452-460.

Idoro, G. I., & Jolaiya, O. (2020). Evaluating material storage strategies and their relationship with construction project performance. *Proceedings of CIB International Conference on Building Education and Research*, University of Cape Town.